

Fig. 1: Radio map of J0000-0541 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 4: Radio map of J0022-1039 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 2: Radio map of J0000-0541 in K band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 18\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 5: Radio map of J0022-1039 in K band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 3: Radio map of J0000-0541 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 6: Radio map of J0203-1247 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 7: Radio map of J0203-1247 in K band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 10: Radio map of J0203-1247 in K band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 19\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 8: Radio map of J0203-1247 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 35\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 11: Radio map of J0203-1247 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 9: Radio map of J0203-1247 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 13\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 12: Radio map of J0212-0201 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 18\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 13: Radio map of J0212-0201 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 13\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 16: Radio map of J0230-0859 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 19\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 14: Radio map of J0212-0201 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 17: Radio map of J0230-0859 in K band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 15: Radio map of J0212-0201 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 18: Radio map of J0230-0859 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 39\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 19: Radio map of J0230-0859 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 22: Radio map of J0239-1118 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 20: Radio map of J0230-0859 in K band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 23: Radio map of J0239-1118 in K band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 21: Radio map of J0230-0859 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 24: Radio map of J0239-1118 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59863. The map rms is $\sigma = 39\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 25: Radio map of J0239-1118 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 28: Radio map of J0400-2500 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 20\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 26: Radio map of J0239-1118 in K band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 29: Radio map of J0400-2500 in K band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 35\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 27: Radio map of J0239-1118 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59902. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 30: Radio map of J0400-2500 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 31: Radio map of J0400-2500 in K band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 34: Radio map of J0422-1854 in K band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 19\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 32: Radio map of J0413-0050 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 35: Radio map of J0422-1854 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 33: Radio map of J0422-1854 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 14\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 36: Radio map of J0422-1854 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 14\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 37: Radio map of J0422-1854 in K band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 40: Radio map of J0436-1022 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 34\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 38: Radio map of J0436-1022 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 96]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 41: Radio map of J0436-1022 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 18\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 39: Radio map of J0436-1022 in K band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 21\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 42: Radio map of J0436-1022 in K band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 43: Radio map of J0436-1022 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 36\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 46: Radio map of J0447-0508 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 32\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 44: Radio map of J0447-0508 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 47: Radio map of J0447-0508 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 45: Radio map of J0447-0508 in K band, observed on MJD 59872. The map rms is $\sigma = 20\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 48: Radio map of J0447-0508 in K band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 26\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 49: Radio map of J0447-0508 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59882. The map rms is $\sigma = 36\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 52: Radio map of J0549-2425 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59898. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 50: Radio map of J0549-2425 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59898. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 53: Radio map of J0549-2425 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59899. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 51: Radio map of J0549-2425 in K band, observed on MJD 59898. The map rms is $\sigma = 20\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 54: Radio map of J0549-2425 in K band, observed on MJD 59899. The map rms is $\sigma = 20\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 55: Radio map of J0549-2425 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59899. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 58: Radio map of J0820-1741 in K band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 56: Radio map of J0820-1741 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 59: Radio map of J0842-0349 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 57: Radio map of J0820-1741 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 60: Radio map of J0842-0349 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 61: Radio map of J0846-1214 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 21\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 96]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 64: Radio map of J0846-1214 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 96]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 62: Radio map of J0846-1214 in K band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 27\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 65: Radio map of J0846-1214 in K band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 63: Radio map of J0846-1214 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 66: Radio map of J0846-1214 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 67: Radio map of J0849-2351 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 16\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 70: Radio map of J0849-2351 in K band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 21\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 68: Radio map of J0849-2351 in K band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 71: Radio map of J0849-2351 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 31\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 69: Radio map of J0849-2351 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 16\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 72: Radio map of J0850-0318 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59883. The map rms is $\sigma = 17\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 73: Radio map of J0850-0318 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59904. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 76: Radio map of J1044-1826 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59862. The map rms is $\sigma = 37\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 74: Radio map of J1044-1826 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59862. The map rms is $\sigma = 20\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 77: Radio map of J1044-1826 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 75: Radio map of J1044-1826 in K band, observed on MJD 59862. The map rms is $\sigma = 33\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 78: Radio map of J1044-1826 in K band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 79: Radio map of J1044-1826 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 30\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 82: Radio map of J1147-2145 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 25\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 80: Radio map of J1147-2145 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 83: Radio map of J2021-2235 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59900. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 96]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 81: Radio map of J1147-2145 in K band, observed on MJD 59903. The map rms is $\sigma = 22\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 84: Radio map of J2021-2235 in K band, observed on MJD 59900. The map rms is $\sigma = 35\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 85: Radio map of J2021-2235 in Ka band, observed on MJD 59900. The map rms is $\sigma = 32\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6, 12, 24]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 86: Radio map of J2244-1822 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59884. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.

Fig. 87: Radio map of J2358-1028 in Ku band, observed on MJD 59884. The map rms is $\sigma = 15\mu\text{Jy}$, the contours are at $[-3, 3, 6]\times\sigma$.